

The culinary art of clinical simulation

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The culinary art of clinical simulation

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1. Oranges

Oranges are one of the most versatile fruits to teach doctors with. Their firm pocked rind makes them perfect to practice taking skin biopsies. Their juicy interior means that they are also fantastic replicas of joints for doctors to learn how to give injections. One of the loveliest examples of using oranges in medical education is their role in teaching students about delivering babies. If you carefully cut out a small circle of peel with a utility knife, keeping the pith intact, you have magically created a dilated cervix and baby's head. All you need to do then is insert the orange into an old sports sock and there is a model of the vagina and uterus of a woman in labour. Teachers can line up several oranges with different size circles cut out, so that students can learn the difference between 2cm and 4cm dilation, by inserting two fingers into the dark sock cavity and feeling the edges of the orange rind. This helps train the doctors' sensory memory and a crucial skill in determining how far away a baby is from being born.

2. Pear Drops

Smell has long been important in clinical diagnosis, with many illnesses leaving traces on the sufferer's breath or in their urine. There were even urine smelling wheels in that past that described odour qualities in a multi-coloured circular array, similar to the wine or coffee tasting flavour wheels that are used today. In clinical practice doctors don't smell urine samples anymore but in medical school they are still trained to use their own noses. Take diabetes. When someone's sugars are too high their breath takes on a sweet fruity smell because of higher levels of ketones. Medical educators simulate this condition with a common sweet called the Pear Drop. Teachers hand out the candy in class for a student to suck on, instructing another to sniff their colleague's breath. The odour released by Pear Drops beautifully mimics that of someone whose sugar levels are not in control. Patients' families and friends can be educated to recognise the distinctive Pear Drop aroma too (also likened to nail polish), so that they can get help for their loved one as soon as possible. Who would have thought that candy could be so good for your health?

3. Eggs

With their delicate shells and inner membranes, eggs make the perfect food for neurosurgeons to practice using drill equipment. There are some tricky and complex areas of operation, such as the anatomical areas around the ear. These parts of the body require great precision in surgery, particularly when dissecting through bone and trying not to damage the fragile structures underneath. Surgeons use eggs to practice drilling with new robotic equipment designed to be highly sensitive to the tissues lying just ahead of its current position. Using the drills on eggs enables surgeons to not only develop their haptic techniques, particularly how much pressure to apply, but also learn how to trust the sensitivity of the tool. New robotic drills will stop drilling once they have gone through the eggshell, only a few millimeters in thickness, but before they touch the membrane separating the shell from the egg white. This is a level of minute perception that humans alone are not capable of. As the anthropologist Neil Stephens writes, practicing on eggs is not only useful for

developing skills, but also becomes a way of making this insensible quality of the drill sensible to the practitioners who will use it.

4. Pigs' trotters

A lot of medical schools now use synthetic skin when training suturing, and there is a big industry in trying to make the skin look and feel as realistic as possible. In the medical schools where I do fieldwork as an anthropologist, there are drawers filled with little pieces of fake skin on plastic bases. When I was in medical school though, my teachers went to the butcher for their supplies. I remember being presented one day in class with a metal tray of cold white pigs' feet, some surgical twine, scalpels, needles and needle holders. Donning gloves we were taught to suture for the first time. As an amateur seamstress I loved playing with needle and thread and making nice neat black stitches in the thick smelly flesh, disconnecting completely from the animal of whose feet lay before me. Many medical schools still use pigs' trotters to teach suturing. In a wonderful study comparing the suturing friendliness of pigs' trotters, beef tongues, hot dogs and latex gloves, researchers found that pigs' trotters were both the cheapest and easiest to work with. So it's no surprise that many medical schools around the world still keep their fridges well stocked.

5. Grapes

Doctors spend years training to become surgeons, including practicing knots on their bedposts and suturing bananas. New techniques are now required as more and more robots enter the operating theatre. Manipulating robotic arms during a surgical procedure takes a specific set of finely tuned bodily movements, where surgeons and machine work together. Enter grapes. Their delicate skins mean that they are perfect for practicing on, as well as demonstrating the wonders of robotic surgery. A few years ago, a video made the rounds showing how a robot called da Vinci could stitch up a small tear in a grape. It was only at the end of the video that you realised the grape was nestled in the base of a narrow necked glass jar. No surgeon was visible except for the arms of the robot, meticulously sewing up the cut in the grape with knots of the finest thread. Some scientists are looking at how surgical robots can magnify the fine skills of humans into even finer parts, allowing for more precision than ever before. As millions are spent on developing these technologies, a simple bunch of grapes is all it takes to show how magnificent they might be.

6. Offal

Butchery and medicine have a long term relationship together. It is one of the reasons surgeons lose their "Dr" title when they become fully trained. Animals have been used to learn medicine since it all began, the ancient Greek physician Galen famously basing his understanding of anatomy on their dissections. While anatomical knowledge has advanced since then, many animal parts are still used to train doctors. Chickens' legs are used by surgical trainees to practice tendon repair for example, while the vessels of drumsticks are useful for vascular techniques, as they are visible to the human eye. Chicken tracheas and beef tongues provide good practice as well. It may be that computer simulation replaces animal parts for reasons of cost and ethics, however, for now these techniques are considered so useful in training both basic and advanced procedures that there are companies which specialise in providing such material for medical education. So teachers no longer have to go

to the local butcher in their lunchbreaks. An English company called Wet Lab for example offers sheep chests, upper/lower mandibles and anal sphincters on their menu, all bi-products of healthy animals which were intended for human consumption.

7. Tropical fruits

Doctors have known about the pedagogical power of fruit for centuries. Since Hippocrates fruits have been used to help describe disease – the yellowing of a patient’s skin due to jaundice being likened to pomegranate peel for example. Teachers use metaphors to help students remember conditions: strawberry tongue for scarlet fever, raspberry tongue means late stage disease. When it comes to simulating body parts, there are other fruits besides oranges and grapes which are used. Pick almost any fruit from your local market and there is probably some body part it can be likened to. Soft ripe papayas can help train gynaecological procedures like abortions, where students must learn to manipulate instruments through a small opening, reaching inside for the seed-filled cavity of the uterus. Bananas can be cut away to resemble a toenail resection. Peaches are perfect for resembling the skin of a child, so soft and delicate (though rarely so furry). Pregnancy is stereotypically likened to all of the round fruits, the latest stage usually being the watermelon. So it may or may not be of some solace to women in late stage pregnancy, that some doctors also use watermelons to practice inserting epidurals.

Photography by Blommers & Schumm

2 Meat

Butchery and medicine have a longstanding relationship. Animals have been used to learn medicine since it all began—the ancient Greek physician Galen famously being his understanding of anatomy on advanced dissections. While anatomical knowledge has trained doctors, animal parts are still used to train doctors. Chickens' legs are still used to trainees to practise tendon repair, for example, while the vessels in drumsticks are useful for learning to the naked eye. Chicken tracheas and beef tongues are good practice subjects too. It may be that

computer simulation will replace animal parts for reasons of cost and ethics, but for now these techniques are considered so useful in both basic and advanced procedure training that there are companies that specialise in providing such material for medical education—so lecturers no longer have to go to the local butcher during their lunchbreaks. An English company called Wet Lab, for example, offers sheep chests, upper/lower mandibles and anal sphincter on its menu, all by-products from healthy animals butchered for consumption.

3 Eggs

Delicate shells and inner membranes make eggs the perfect food for neurosurgeons to practise using drill equipment. There are some tricky and complex areas of the body to operate on, for instance around the ear. Such areas require great precision in surgery, particularly when dissecting through bone and trying not to damage the fragile structures beneath. Surgeons use eggs to practise with new robotic drills designed to be highly sensitive to the tissues lying just ahead of their current position. Using the drills on eggs enables surgeons not only to develop their haptic techniques (those requiring accurate touch),

but also to learn how to trust the sensitivity of the tool. New robotic drills will stop drilling once they have gone through the eggshell, only a few millimetres in thickness, but before they touch the membrane separating the shell from the white. This is a level of minute perception that unassisted humans are not capable of. As the anthropologist Neil Stephens has written, practising on eggs is not only useful for developing skills, it also becomes a way of making this insensible quality of the drill sensible to the practitioners who will use it.

4 Fruit

Doctors have known about the pedagogical power of fruit for centuries. Since the days of Hippocrates, the yellowing of a patient's skin due to jaundice being likened to pomegranate peel, for example. Lecturers use metaphors to help students remember conditions: strawberry tongue for scarlet fever, raspberry tongue means late-stage disease. When it comes to simulating body parts, there are other fruits besides oranges and grapes that are used. Pick almost any fruit from your local market and there's probably some body part it can be likened to. Soft ripe

papayas can be used in the training of gynaecological procedures such as abortions, where students must learn to manipulate instruments through a small opening, reaching inside for the seed-filled cavity of the uterus. Bananas can be cut away to mimic a foetal resection. Peaches are perfect in resembling the skin of a child, soft and delicate (though usually furrier). The stages of pregnancy are typically likened to round fruits—so it may or may not be of some solace to women in late-stage pregnancy to hear that some doctors use watermelons to practise inserting epidurals.

5 Pigs' trotters

Many medical schools now use synthetic skin to train students in suturing, and there's a big industry in trying to make the skin look and feel as realistic as possible. In the schools where I do fieldwork as an anthropologist, there are drawers filled with little pieces of fake skin on plastic bases. When I was a medical student, though, my tutors went to the butcher for their supplies. I remember being presented one day in class with a metal tray of cold, white pigs' feet, some surgical twine, scalpels, needles and needle holders. Gloves donned, we were taught to suture for the first time. As an amateur seamstress I loved play-

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Bio

Anna Harris writes about medicine and other crafts, and thinks through food. A doctor and an anthropologist, her current work at Maastricht University is funded by the European Research Council under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (grant agreement No. 678390): www.makingclinicalsense.com. You can read more on her website www.annaroseharris.wordpress.com and blog www.pneumaticpost.blogspot.com